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Impact of Community Participation on Effective Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State Local Government Education Authorities

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Abstract

The study was on the Impact of Community Participation on Effective Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State Local Government Education Authorities and two objectives and corresponding research questions were formulated to guide the study. The descriptive survey design method was adopted for the study which was conducted in all the eleven Local Education Authorities of Gombe State with a population of 4604 (3565 male & 1039 female) education stakeholders within all the eleven local education Authorities in Gombe state during the 2018/2019 academic session. The sample of 379 (292 male & 87 female) education stakeholders were selected using simple random sampling technique by hat and draw method. The data for this study were gathered through the use of a questionnaire titled “community involvement on the implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme questionnaire” (CIIOUEP). To ensure the validity of the instrument used, two experts in the area of research measurement were contacted to read through and made comments and observations on the items contained on the questionnaire. The test and retest method was used in two schools where the questionnaire was administered to them and collected after 2 weeks and it was redone. The reliability test had a α value 0.86. The data was analysed using mean and standard deviation and the Grand mean to take decisions. The study revealed that effective community participation is very imperative for the realization of the Universal Basic Education objective in Gombe State. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that aggressive mobilization and sensitization visit to the various stakeholders should be indulged by the management of the Gombe State Universal Basic Education Board and they should endeavour to create forum to be meeting at intervals with the various communities.

Keywords: Influence, Community, Involvement, Implementation

Introduction

The emphasis on multi-sectorial approaches to solving the problems of poverty, and other human development challenges in the developing societies of the world has become the emerging trend since the turn of the new millennium. This paradigm shift is influenced by the premises that the resources available at the disposal of the government is inadequate to cater for the enormous challenges facing mankind in his social environment. This therefore means, the government, the private sector, community and other relevant stakeholders must partner and collaborate. This new approach has been described by developmentalists as Public Private Partnership (PPP) approach to addressing the human development challenges in the society. It is within the context of the above that the whole concept of community participation in the running of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) Programme of the federal government came into being. The concept of community participation in the

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provision of social services has been described as bottom-up approach to development. According to Egwu (2004) in Zubairu (2020), it is an evolving concept which builds on community resources, expertise, supplies and the best way to utilize the development Latent Potentials which are abundant in the communities.

The Universal Basic Education Programme of the federal government was a brain-child of the Chief Olusegun Obasanjo's administration on assumption of office as President and Commander in Chief of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in 1999, he inaugurated and launched the UBEC programme in Sokoto. The UBE Programme is a current educational reform which focuses on the issues of access, equity and quality in the delivery of Basic Education. The Programme is intended to provide a free, compulsory, Universal Basic Education for every Nigerian child of school age as contained in the enabling law, UBE Act of 2004. The programme is primarily aimed at eradicating illiteracy, ignorance and poverty in all facets in Nigeria because education is regarded as the panacea to human and development problems of any society. The objectives of the UBE Programme as contained in the UBE Act of 2004: includes among others developing in the entire citizenry a strong consciousness for education and a strong commitment to its vigorous promotion, provision of free, Universal Basic Education for every child of school age; reducing drastically the incidence of school dropout from formal school system; catering for the learning needs of young persons who for one reason or another have had to interrupt their schooling through appropriate form of complementary approaches to the promotion of basic education; and ensuring the acquisition of the appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, communicative and life civil values needed for laying a sound and solid foundation for Life-Long Learning (UBE Act, 2004).

Communities as major stakeholders in the Universal Basic Education Project are expected to collaborate with the government in the following areas in the implementation of Basic Education; Prompt repair and renovation of blown-off school roofs; Construction/innovation of school through Self-help; Mobilization for enrolment of School Aged Children in schools; Provision of infrastructural and Instructional materials in school to support effort of Government; Assistance in procurement of books for School Libraries to improve reading and writing skill of Pupils; Provision of school Uniform and books to wards/children; Assist in provision of Teaching/Learning materials in Schools; Pooling of resources to assist the schools in areas of needs; Provision of friendly environment for teaching/learning in School; Encourage enrolment and retention of pupils in school and Checkmate Child Trafficking through enrolment of School Aged Children (UBE Act, 2004).

The Universal Basic Education (UBE) Programme being a programme of the federal government is implemented in the 36 States of the Federation including the federal capital territory through the various States Universal Basic Education Boards (SUBEB). It is on the background of the above that this research work, "Impact of Community involvement on Implementation of UBE Programme in Gombe State" will be investigated.

The realization of the Universal Basic Education Programme of the federal government requires the collaboration of state government with communities and other stakeholders. Based on the implementation blueprint, Communities are expected to perform certain roles which include: ensuring the maintenance of infrastructure and facilities for the UBE programme in their local schools; prompt responds to renovation of blown-off school roofs through Community Self-help Initiative; Mobilization for enrollment/retention of pupils in school; provision of logistic support and enabling environment for the implementation of the UBE programme; assisting government to address challenges of out-of-school children in the State; identifying and responding to the needs of the schools among others. There is dearth of information on the level of Influence and participation of Community Members in the implementation of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) Programme in Gombe state Zubairu (2020). Therefore, it is imperative to ascertain whether communities are actually addressing the roles indicated in the implementation blueprint adequately and at the same time influencing the programme positively.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to examine Impact of Community Participation on Effective Implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State Local Government Education Authorities. Specifically, the purpose of the study is to determine the following:

1. The level of community contributions in the provision of infrastructural/instructional materials for the UBE programme in schools that will influence the programme effectiveness.
2. The level to which parents give their wards support toward educational development.

Research Questions

1. To what extent do contribution of members of the community in the provision of infrastructure and instructional materials in the UBE Programme in the state influence the effectiveness of the programme?
2. What is the extent of parental contribution to the education of the children/wards in the UBE Programme in the state?

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Methodology

The study adopted the survey design on which Groves, Fowler, Couper, James, Singer & Tourangeau, (2004,) in Jansen (2010) sees it as, "The survey is a systematic method for gathering information from (a sample of) entities for the purpose of constructing quantitative descriptors of the attributes of the larger population of which the entities are members." Gombe State is located in the North Eastern part of Nigeria with its capital in Gombe. It shares common borders with the states of Borno, Yobe, Taraba, Adamawa and Bauchi. The population for this study was 1247 public Primary Schools and 285 junior secondary schools in the Communities spread across the 11 Local Government Areas of the State with uneven distribution of schools. Descriptive survey design method was adopted for the study which was conducted in all the eleven Local Education Authorities of Gombe State with a population of 4604 (3565 male & 1039 female) education stakeholders within all the eleven local education Authorities in Gombe state during the 2018/2019 academic session. The sample for this study was generated using the R.V. Krejcie and D.W. Morgan table 379 (292 male & 87 female) education stakeholders were selected using simple random sampling technique by hat and draw method. The data for this study were gathered through the use of a questionnaire titled "community involvement on the implementation of Universal Basic Education Programme questionnaire" (CIIOUEP). Twenty questions were set (ten for each research question) to guide the research. To ensure the validity of the instrument used, two experts in the area of research measurement were contacted to read through and made comments and observations on the items contained on the questionnaire. The test and retest method was used in two schools where the questionnaire was administered to them and collected after 2 weeks and it was redone. Reliability test done had a α value of 0.86. The data was analysed using mean (\bar{x}) and standard deviation (σ) and the Grand mean to take decisions. The decision rule considered was that a mean rating of 2.0 and above was positive while a mean rating that is below 2.0 was considered as negative.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does contribution of members of the community in the provision of infrastructure and instructional materials in the UBE programme in the state influence the programme effectiveness?

S/ N.	Provision of Infrastructural/ Instructional Materials for Teaching/ Learning	Mean (\bar{x})	STD(σ)	Remarks
1	The school-based management committees in my school support the school by provision of instructional materials	2.4	1.0	P.E
2	The school-based management committees and other stakeholders provide furniture for teachers without waiting for government.	2.5	0.7	ME
3	The existence of the school Based Management Committee, PTA and other stakeholders provide relevant material and facilities for teaching/ learning in the school.	2.7	1.0	M.E
4	Parent and other stakeholders provide books for the school libraries in my community	2.3	1.1	S.E
5	Community members often assist volunteers/UBE teachers posted to my school in areas of transport accommodation.	4.0	0.9	G.E
6	The PTA members sometimes assist the school in my area with books, and other instructional materials. Parental support is very necessary for the implementation of Basic Education delivery in my area.	2.8	1.0	M.E
7	Members of the community and other stakeholders at the grass root regularly participate in making decision and implementing polities that affect physical facilities.	3.3	0.9	M.E
8	Community and other stakeholders help in the procurement of teaching/leaning materials for the school.	2.2	1.0	S.E
9	Parents and community members do support in the provision of school libraries and other reading materials.	2.1	1.1	G.E
10	Members of the PTA in my school often assist the school in preparation and use of locally available learning materials and resources.	2.5	0.8	M.E
Grand Mean		2.6		

Source: Field Survey 2018

Table 1 shows the responses of stakeholders on perception on how their contributions of infrastructure and instructional materials influence the UBE programme effectiveness. The result shows that the mean

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of the stakeholders ranged between 2.1 to 4.0 with standard deviation ranging between 0.7 to 1.0 indicating that a poor extent to a great extent with a grand mean of 2.6 indicating a moderate extent of contributions of community members in the provision of infrastructure materials in the UBE programme implementation in the state.

KEY~ PE-Poor Extent; ME-Moderate Extent; GE-Good Extent; SE-Strong Extent

Research Question 2

To what extent does parental support for the education of their child/wards influence the UBE programme in the state?

S/N	Items:	MEAN (\bar{x})	STD (σ)	Remarks
Parental Support for Children/Wards Education				
1	Parents/Guardians in my area usually equip their ward for school by providing them with uniform.	2.6	1.1	M.E
2	Parents/Guardians in my area usually equip their ward for school by providing them with books and other relevant materials to achieve UBE Programme.	3.2	1.6	G.E
3	The stakeholders discourage certain aspect of traditional norms and practices education in my community.	2.3	1.1	S.E
4	Many parents were sensitized on the importance of basic education as means to achieve self-reliance and contribution to economic development of a community/state.	3.5	0.4	S.E
5	Some parents prefer sending their wards to acquire vocational skills rather than enrolling them for basic education.	3.8	1.2	M.E
6	Parental support is very necessary for the implementation of Basic Education delivery in my area.	4.6	0.4	G.E
7	Because of poverty and poor economic background of some parents, they prefer sending their wards to acquire vocational skills rather than enrolling them for Basic Education.	3.6	0.8	G.E
8	Child trafficking still exist in my community in spite of the existence of UBE law.	3.3	1.0	M.E
9	Parents advices their wards on the need for Education.	2.9	0.9	M.E
10	Parents in my area gives moral support.	3.0	1.1	M.E
	Grand Mean	3.2		

Source: Field Survey 2018

Table 2 List of variables were generated and the respondents were asked to indicate the extent to which they agree or disagreed with the variables that influence parental support in the implementation of the programme. The result shows the mean of stakeholders on parental support ranging from 2.3 to 4.6 with standard deviation of ranging from 0.4 to 1.2 indicating from a poor extent to a great extent with a grand mean of 3.2 indicating a moderate extent of parental support for children/ward's Education in the various communities in the implementation of the UBE programme of the state.

Discussion of Findings

The first Research question of this study explored the level of community participation and the influence on the implementation of the UBE Community Initiated Self-help project in schools. The Universal Basic Education Programme stresses on active community participation and involvement in the renovation/construction of school blocks through Self-help to enhance effective teaching/learning environment. This finding agrees with the position of Zubairu (2020) in his justification of the need for community participation in the delivery of Basic education in Nigeria. According to him, Basic Education like any social service cannot be left in the hand of government alone, that stakeholders including the community should pool resources together to enhance the successful delivery of basic education. He further posited that the involvement of community is a strategy to galvanize grassroots and stakeholders support for Education Service delivery to achieve Education for All. The findings from the study also justifies the call for community participation in Basic education programme as contain in the UBE

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Act of 2004 and CRS Law No. I of 2006 – including other policy framework and Federal Ministry of Education documents which stressed the need for involvement of communities and stakeholders in the Management and implementation of Basic education.

The second research question for this study explored the level of community participation and its influence on the increase/retention of pupils in schools for the attainment of the objective of the Universal Basic Education Programme. The objective of the UBE Programme is to provide free Universal Basic Education for every Child of school age; reduce drastically the incidence of school dropout amongst others. Otu (2002) in Usman (2018) spoke on the need for parents and community members to support the school in provision of child friendly school environment for effective teaching and learning to take place. This is in the area of provision of teaching/learning materials, provision of seats and learning environment among others to complement the effort of the government for the effective delivery of Basic Education in Gombe State.

From the above, it's apparent that increase and retention of pupils for the actualization of the Universal Basic Education Programme in Gombe State is dependent on active community participation. Regrettably, the community is not rendering the expected level of participation to ginger increased enrolment in public schools in the State to enhance the success of the Universal Basic Education Programme. It was observed from the field study that, in some communities/areas like Nomadic and Migrant Schools, teachers still appeal to Parents to allow their wards attend schools. Some parents in these settlements prefer their wards especially the boy-child to go farming or rearing animal which will bring immediate income to support the home rather than remain in the school. It was also observed that other socio-cultural factors tend to prevent parent from sending their boy-child or even girl-child to school. This no doubt will impede the realization of the universal basic programme of the federal government.

Conclusion

The conclusion drawn from the findings of this study is that effective Community Participation is very imperative for the realization of the Universal Basic Education Programme of the Government in Gombe State.

Communities should be actively involved in the implementation of the Community Initiated Self-help Projects of the Universal Basic Education Programme. Through this the Challenges of blown-off school roofs, dilapidated School buildings and infrastructure decays etc will be promptly addressed which will facilitate the realization of the objective of the UBE in the State. Active Mobilization and Sensitization of Parents and Community Members on the Universal Basic Education Programme will lead to increase in enrollment and retention of pupil in school for the realization of the Universal Basic Education Programme in the state. Community support to schools in the provision of infrastructural and instructional materials for effective teaching and learning is very essential if the objective of the Universal Basic Education Programme is to be achieved in the state. Lastly, parents and guardians should regularly give educational support to their wards through provision of relevant text-books/reading materials, uniform and other necessary material needed for school. Through these, the objectives of the UBE programme can be achieved since Government alone cannot achieve this.

Recommendations

From the foregoing, it has been observed that active community participation is very imperative for the realization of the Universal Basic Programme (UBE) of the federal government. Regrettably, the level of community participation in Basic Education Programme in Gombe State does not give the desired encouragement to realize the objectives of the Universal Basic Education programme as conceived by the Enabling Laws, UBE Act of 2004 and Gombe State UBE Law No 1of 2006. This therefore means certain measures must be taken to encourage maximum community participation in the implementation of the Universal Basic Education Programme. The following recommendations are hereby made as a way of boosting or encouraging community involvement or participation in the provision of Basic Education since government alone cannot do it.

1. There is need for regular sensitization and creation of awareness to parents and community members to be actively involved in the implementation of the community-initiated self-help projects of the Universal Basic Education Programme in the State. Through this, the challenges of infrastructural delay, dilapidated school block and furniture will be reduced.
2. The State Ministry of Education (SMOE), and State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) should use proper mechanism to encourage community members, parents and guardians on the need to assist schools in the provision of needed infrastructural and instructional material which will enhance effective teaching and learning in schools.
3. Aggressive Mobilization and Sensitization visit to Traditional rulers, Parent Teachers Association members, members of the School Based Management Committee (SMBC), religious organizations, market women and other stakeholders at the grassroot to support school programmes, encourage enrollment/retention of pupils in schools.

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4. The Management of the Gombe State Universal Basic Education Board should endeavour to create a forum where they can meet at intervals with members of Parent Teachers Association, of schools, and appeal to them to provide their wards with relevant textbooks, uniform and other materials needed for school.
5. The Board should create a proper synergy with traditional rulers in the various communities to regularly mobilize their subjects using the villager Town Criers to send their wards to school for increase enrollment and retention for the UBE Programme.
6. The Board and Local Government Education Authorities should at the beginning of every academic session, air jingles on UBE enrollment in the Radio and Television appealing to parents to send their wards to schools and also provide them with relevant materials for school.

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